

THE ROLE OF DIDACTIC GAMES AND EXERCISES IN THE FORMATION OF ORAL SPEECH IN PRIMARY SCHOOL STUDENTS

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Abstract. *This article reveals the importance of didactic games and exercises in the development of oral speech in primary school students. The author analyzes the psychological and pedagogical foundations of speech development in young children and substantiates the positive influence of game forms of learning on the expansion of vocabulary, the strengthening of grammatical structure, and the formation of communicative competence. The article presents effective types of games and exercises aimed at developing oral speech, as well as methodological recommendations for teachers.*

Keywords: *didactic game, oral speech, elementary school, exercises, speech development, elementary education, communication skills.*

Introduction. Mastering oral speech is one of the most important tasks of primary education. It is at this age that the foundations of oral and written speech are formed in children, which plays an important role in the subsequent educational process and socialization.

The formation of oral speech involves not only memorizing words and grammatical rules, but also involving the child in active speech communication. One of the most effective tools in this process is didactic games and exercises.

Play is a leading type of activity for children, therefore it has great potential for speech development in the educational process. And exercises help to consolidate the acquired knowledge and skills. Together, these two forms form in children the skills of free expression of thought, constructing correct sentences, entering into communication, and demonstrating speech activity.

Theoretical foundations of games and exercises in speech development. As L.S. Vygotsky noted, the development of speech is closely related to the child's activity and communication. During play, the child uses speech freely and naturally. This allows not only to master language tools, but also to develop speech behavior, thinking, memory, and imagination.

A.N. Leontyev emphasized that game forms of learning create internal motivation in the child: the child speaks not because it is "necessary," but because it is "interesting." In play, the fear of mistakes decreases, which is especially important for children with underdeveloped speech or lack of self-confidence.

Methodological approaches. With the help of didactic games and exercises in organizing lessons in primary grades, the following aspects are formed in students:

- lexical and grammatical skills are developed;
- pronunciation and hearing are strengthened;
- connected speech is formed;
- interest in language learning increases;
- a natural communication environment is created.

Usually, didactic games and exercises can be divided into types according to their purpose.

1. Games for vocabulary development:

- "Find the redundant word";
- "Find a synonym or antonym";
- "Tell me in one word."

2. Games aimed at forming grammatical structure:

- "Tell me truth";
- "Change the word into plural";
- "Make a sentence with words."

3. Games aimed at developing connected speech:

- "Tell a fairy tale";
- "Convey the message";
- "Describe the picture";
- "Continue the Story."

4. Games for the development of dialogic speech:

Role-playing games (*stores, hospitals, schools, etc.*);

- "Interview";
- "Telephone Conversation."

5. Phonetic games:

- "Repeat correctly";
- "Find the voiced word";
- "Quick Exercises."

Sample game exercises

1. "Magic Bag". The teacher takes an object from the bag and asks the child to describe it without naming it. The rest find the item.

2. "Who am I?". A picture of an animal or object is attached to the student's forehead. He asks questions, and the classmates answer "yes" or "no." The goal is to find out who he is.

3. "A Story Based on Pictures". A sequence of 3-5 pictures is given. The student composes a story based on them.

4. "Correct the Mistake". The teacher deliberately makes grammatical errors, and the students correct and explain them.

5. "Microphone". The student takes the toy microphone and expresses their opinion on the given topic, while others listen and ask questions.

Effectiveness of games in practice

Practice shows that didactic games and exercises:

- increases the speech activity of students;
- reinforces grammatical and pronunciation skills;
- expands vocabulary;
- develops the ability to communicate confidently;
- Increases interest in learning.

Teachers emphasize that even sluggish or shy children actively participate in the game and try to express their thoughts.

Methodological recommendations for teachers

1. Games should be used regularly.
2. Selection of tasks in accordance with the age and speech level of students.
3. Use games not only for explanation but also at the consolidation stage.
4. Support not only the correct answer, but any speech activity.
5. Create a comfortable, interesting, and free communication environment in the classroom.

Conclusion. Didactic games and exercises are an important tool in the development of oral speech of primary school students. They not only increase students' interest in language, but also create opportunities for natural and effective speech development. The game approach serves to implement an individual approach, ensure the activity of all students, and especially the formation of communicative skills in children with underdeveloped speech.

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